

SINONIMLAR VA ULARNING USLUBIY XOSSALARI

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ANNOTATSIYA: Ma'nodosh so'zlar bir ma'noni xilma xil so'zlar orqali turli nozik ma'no qirralari bilan ifodalashda, so'z sehrini namoyish etishda, nutqni bezashda, ta'sirchanligini taminlashda katta ahamiyatga ega

Kalit so'zlar: Sinonimlar, sinonimlarning uslubiyatdagi o'rni, hissiy bo'yoqdorlik, ijobiy va salbiy bo'yoqdorlik.

Ma'nodosh so'zlar bir umumiy manoni ifodalovchi ikki yoki undan ortiq so'zlardir. Bir umumiy manosi bilan o'zaro bog'lanuvchi so'zlar guruhi sinonimik qator deyiladi. Sinonimik qator ikki yoki undan ortiq so'zlardan tashkil topadi. Har bir sinonimik qatorda bir so'z asosiy so'z hisoblanadi. Bu so'z barcha uslublarda qo'llana oladi, shuning uchun neytral so'z, betaraf so'z, dominanta atamallari bilan nomlanadi. Masalan, nazar solmoq, boqmoq, qaramoq sinonimik qatorida bosh so'z qaramoq dominanta hisoblanadi.

Sinonimik qatordagi so'zlar hissiy bo'yoqdorligiga ko'ra o'zaro farqlanishi mumkin: hissiy bo'yoqdor so'zlar va hissiy bo'yoqsiz so'zlar. Hissiy bo'yoqdor so'zlar ijobiy yoki salbiylik xususiyatiga ega. Masalan: yuz, aft, bet, bashara, turq, chehra, oraz, ruxsor, uzor kabi sinonimik qatorda aft, bashara, turq, bet so'zlari salbiy baho munosabatini ifodalaydi. Oraz, ruxsor, uzor, chehra so'zlari ijobiy munosabatni ifodalaydi. Shulardan uzor, ruxsor, oraz so'zlari badiiy uslubga xoslanish belgisi mavjud. Sinonimik qatordagi so'zlar nutqning biror turiga, uslubiga xosligi jihatidan ham farqlanishi mumkin. Masalan, sovg'a, hadya, tortiq, armug'on, tuhfa sinonimik qatorida tuhfa va armug'on so'zlari kitobiy uslubga xos. Urishmoq, yoqalashmoq, solishmoq, mushtlashmoq, so'qishmoq, tashashmoq sinonimik qatoridagi solishmoq, so'qishmoq, tashashmoq so'zlari oddiy so'zlashuv uslubiga xos. Sinonimik qatordagi so'z adabiy tilga yoki shevaga ham oid bo'lishi mumkin. Masalan, ovoz, tovush, un, sas so'zlarida sas; qidirmoq, izlamoq, istamoq so'zlaridagi istamoq so'zi shevaga xos so'z hisoblanadi. Ifodalaydigan tushuncha doirasi keng bo'lgan, belgini meyoriy darajada ifodalaydigan, hissiy bo'yoqqa ega bo'lmagan, hozirgi adabiy tilga mansub bo'lgan so'z sinonimik qatordagi so'zlarga nisbatan ko'p qo'llanadi.

Til birliklari bir xil ma'noga ega bo'lish hodisasi sinonimiya deyiladi. Bu hodisa qanday til birliklariga xosligiga qarab, lugaviy (leksik) sinonimiya, frazeologik sinonimiya, sintaktik sinonimiya kabilarga bo'linadi. O'zaro sinonim bulgan so'zlar guruhi Sinonimlar qatori deyiladi. Sinonimlarlar qatori 2 va undan ortiq so'zdan tashkil topadi. Mas, buloq — chashma Sinonimlar qatori 2 so'zdan, yuz—aft — bashara — bet... Sinonimlar qatori esa ko'p so'zlardan tuzilgan. Ko'p ma'noli suzlar muayyan ma'nosi yoki ma'nolari bilan bir yoki birdan ortiq sinonimlar qatoriga kirishi mumkin. Masalan, bitirmoq so'zi bir ma'nosi bilan tugatmoq, tugallamoq, tamomlamoq... so'zlari qatoriga, boshqa ma'nosi bilan ado qilmoq, yo'qotmoq, yo'q qilmoq suzlari qatoriga kiradi.

Sinonimlar qatoridagi bir suz bosh so'z (asosiy so'z) hisoblanadi. Bosh so'z, odatda, hozirgi adabiy tilga mansubligi, emotsional bo'yoq, uslubga ko'ra betarafligi va shu kabi xususiyatlari bilan shu qatordagi boshqa so'zlardan farkanadi hamda xuddi shu xususiyatlariga ko'ra tilda boshqalariga nisbatan keng quotlandadi. Masalan, chiroyli, go'zal, husnli, husndor, xushro'y, ko'hli, zebo, suluv, sohibjamol... Sinonimlar qatorida chiroyli so'zi shunday belgilarga ega va bosh so'z hisoblakadi. Qolgan so'zlar esa har biri o'ziga xos belgixususiyati bilan boshqalaridan farkanadi: go'zal so'zi belgini kuchli (yuqori) daraja bilan ifodalaydi; barno, zebo so'zlari ko'proq kitobiy uslubga ega, suluv so'zi esa nisbatan kam qo'llanadi va hokazolar. Nutqda sinonimlarning har biridan ularga xos belgixususiyatlarni hisobga olgan holda foydalanish muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Sinonimlar shaxs, narsa, belgi, xususiyat, voqeaning bir necha nom bilan aytilishidir. Sinonimlar til boyligi bo'lib, avvalo shaxs va predmetlarning eng nozik mano bo'yoqlarini ifodalash uchun xizmat qiladi.

Ушбу мақолада ўқув луғатларининг умумий луғатлардан нафақат ҳажми, балки ундаги сўзларнинг танланиш мезонлари, луғат қисмларининг таркиби, жойлашуви – мегаструктураси билан ҳам фарқланиши, синоним ўқув луғатлар луғат мақоласи таркибида лексикографик пометалар (турли қисқартмалар, белгилар)га кам ўрин берилганлиги муҳокама қилинади.¹

¹ Гуландом Мирханова. (2022). СИНОНИМ СЎЗЛАР ЎҚУВ ЛУҒАТИНИНГ УМУМИЙ ТУЗИЛИШИ. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(2), 172–178. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/90>

This article is dedicated to the research of Adjusted meanings of Moral-spiritual concept defining units in the Uzbek language. And also analyzed the semantic analysis of grammatical shape lexemes of specialized meaning and provide a corresponding recommendation for lexicographical practice in the Uzbek language is one of the actual challenges of linguistics as today's challenge.²

Корпус лингвистикасида семантик разметка, унинг теглар тизими, тег категориялари, семантик теглаш муаммолари, кўпмаънолилик ва омонимлик муаммосини ечиш масаласига оид қатор тадқиқотлар вужудга келган.³

The article discusses the research methods of Uzbek language syntax. In Uzbek linguistics, syntactic phenomena have been studied in detail since the 1930s, and several syntactic theories have emerged in this regard.⁴

The article examines the first dictionary in the Turkish language Mahmud Kashgaris “Devonu lugotit turk” in terms of a dictionary in accordance with the traditions of world lexicography and argues that it is the first appearance of modern complex dictionaries in the Turkish (Uzbek) language.⁵

Now studying scientific heritage, socio-political activities and acquaintance youth charity of our above-stated ancestors is considered one of the main urgent objectives of the modern intellectuals.⁶

This article covers the main place of small business and business in today's market economy. Including scientifically analyzed the development of small business and business, and the legal

² Gulbahor, T. (2016). Adjusted Meanings of Moral-Spiritual Concept Defining Units. *ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies*, 5(7), 40-45.

³ Ахмедова, Д. (2020). Семантик разметка тизимида тег гуруҳлари. *Oriental Art and Culture*, (III), 440-444.

⁴ Ergashevna, Y. N. (2021). ON METHODS OF RESEARCH OF UZBEK LANGUAGE SYNTAX. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(11), 22-28.

⁵ Bakhriddinova, B. M. (2020). “DEVONU LUGOTIT TURK” AS A FIRST VIEW OF MODERN COMPLEX EDUCATIONAL DICTIONARIES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 981-985.

⁶ Tolibjonovich, M. T. (2021). EASTERN RENAISSANCE AND ITS CULTURAL HERITAGE: THE VIEW OF FOREIGN RESEARCHERS. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(05), 211-215.

basis, at this time financially support small business and business, the latter is amended and the rules for this branch of national legislation are added.⁷

Мамлакатимиз тараққиётининг янги босқичида жамият ҳаётининг асосий негизи бўлмиш оилалар барқарор муҳитини мустаҳкамлаш ва бу масалаларда хотин-қизларнинг ўрни ва аҳамияти ошириш долзарб аҳамият касб этмоқда. Юртимиз аҳолисининг тенг ярмига яқинроғини ташкил этадиган хотин-қизлар жамиятнинг барча соҳаларида самарали фаолият юритмоқда.⁸

In this article are given the importance, role, types of the family in modern society. Its development from ancient times till present is widely described in this article.⁹

The widespread introduction of new pedagogical technologies in teaching students of higher educational institutions and the effective use of innovative technologies are the main support for improving the quality of education.¹⁰

The article describes in detail the basics of translation theory, the object of research, and the methods of analysis of translation theory. Opinions on the importance of translation among different peoples, the concept of translation, and its types are discussed. However, various examples of translation types are given.¹¹

The aim of the present study was to determine whether an association exists between the duration of menopause and the age of menopause onset, and the differences in bone mineral density (BMD) in postmenopausal women.¹²

⁷ Tolibjonovich, Madumarov T., and Gulomjonov O. R. Ogli. "Lombard Microcredit Organization Its Concept and Its Importance Today." *JournalNX*, vol. 6, no. 10, 2020, pp. 109-111.

⁸ Мадумарова Зиёдахон. (2022). ЯНГИЛАНАЁТГАН ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ГЕНДЕР МУАММОЛАРИНИ БАРТАРАФ ЭТИШДА АХЛОҚИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРИНИНГ ЎРНИ. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6569712>

⁹ Nasriddinovich, A. A. (2020). THE FEATURES OF APPEARING FAMILY IN MODERN SOCIETY. *European science review*, (3-4), 69-72.

¹⁰ Jamoliddinovich, U. B. (2022). FUNDAMENTALS OF EDUCATION QUALITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(01), 149-151.

¹¹ Gafurovna, R. Z. (2021). Translation Theory: Object of Research and Methods of Analysis. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*, 24(2), 35-40.

¹² Najmutdinova, D. K., Nurmukhamedova, L. S., Alieva, D. A., Maksudova, D. S., & Nosirova, Z. A. (2016). Study of the effects of the age at menopause and duration of menopause on bone mineral density in postmenopausal women in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Biomedicine*, 6(1), 38-40.

This article analyzes how Somerset Maugham's short story "A Friend in Need" skillfully reflects the power and value of true friendship using ethical concepts such as goodness, kindness, justice, and compassion, which are sacred to each of us.¹³

The article considers the correlation of the real facts and imagination in "Tamburlaine the Great" by Christopher Marlowe.¹⁴

This article discusses an attitude to women in the past and the interpretation of the image of women in the works of some writers.¹⁵

В современном обществе все более возрастает роль иностранных языков. Знание иностранного языка дает молодежи возможность приобщиться к мировой культуре, использовать в своей деятельности потенциал обширных ресурсов глобальной сети Интернет, а также работать с информационными и коммуникационными технологиями и мультимедийными средствами обучения.¹⁶

This article deals with the heroes of the novel "Between Two Doors", one of the most popular works of modern Uzbek literature. There is a comprehensive analysis of the female image. A special place in the work of Utkir Khashimov is occupied by the novel "Between Two Doors". The writer is concerned not only with the pressing social issues of today, but with eternal moral problems. In particular, by calling "Between Two Doors", the writer means the path of person, which he walked from birth to death.¹⁷

Har bir millat madaniyatida kasallik nomlarini ifodalovchi qarashlar mavjud bo'lib ular shu xalq dunyoqarashini, dinini, urf-odatlarini, turmush tarzini va tarixini o'zida mujassamlashtiradi. Xususan, o'zbek va ingliz xalqi amaliy nutqida rak, sil, vabo kabi xavfli kasalliklar nomi qadimda

¹³ Pulatova Sabina. (2022). THE REVELATION OF VIRTUE THROUGH EVIL IN THE SHORT STORY "A FRIEND IN NEED" BY WILLIAM SOMERSET MAUGHAM. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(2), 240–244. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/100>

¹⁴ Temirovna, M. P. (2021). THE CORRELATION OF HISTORICAL TRUTH AND IMAGINATION IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE'S TRAGEDY "TAMBURLAINE THE GREAT". *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(12), 455-457.

¹⁵ Muradovich, R. M. (2021). The Image of a Woman in The Work of Uzbek Writers. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 3, 7-12.

¹⁶ Махмурова, М., Абдуллаева, Л. С., & Самадова, С. А. Современные методы преподавания иностранных языков. Коммуникативный метод. *Наука. Мысль*, 6, 72-76.

¹⁷ Turaeva, K., & Zarinabonu, A. (2022). Interpretation Of Woman Image in Modern Uzbek Literature (Based on Utkir Khashimov's Book "Between Two Doors"). *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 4, 42-44.

tabulashtirilgan, bunga tarixiy sabablar mavjud. Hozirgi kunda ularning davosi topilgan bo'lsada, xalqimiz "yomon xastalik", "og'ir dard", "yomon kasallik" kabi birikmalarni qo'llash bilan kifoyalanadi.¹⁸

Badiiy adabiyotning qamrov darajasi keng sanaladi. Zero undagi janrlarning har biri insonning kamoloti uchun xizmat qiladi.¹⁹

В данной статье сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского.²⁰

В настоящее время глобальной социальной опасностью является угроза обнищания населения. Безработица, экономическая и социальная нестабильность, несбыточность надежд, крушение планов интенсифицируют процесс маргинализация населения.²¹

The relevance of speech and culture in the present day is considered important in linguistics and its areas of study are becoming more and more comprehensive day by day. This article will highlight the important aspects of the study of culture and national characteristics in the study of modern units of oral speech. Currently, English is widely spoken in the world community. It is the language of Advanced Science and technology, trade and cultural relations, trade and business.²²

The article is dedicated to the description of Uzbek national children's clothes of the past centuries and its modern implementation. Article describes types of clothes, its designation and modern usage.²³

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

¹⁸ Baxronova Matluba. (2022). RUHIY KASALLIKLARNING INGLIZ ADABIYOTIDA BERILISHI.

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¹⁹ Oripova Kamola. (2022). O'ZBEK VA FRANSUZ TILLARIDAGI MAQOLLARDA JON KONSEPTINING IFODALANISHI. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnali*, 1(3), 398–408. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/209>

²⁰ Тухтаева, Ф. И., & Хамроева, Ш. Ш. (2019). Сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского. *Мировая наука*, (5), 709-713.

²¹ Суяров, З. Э. (2021). СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКОЕ ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ БЕДНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(12), 1175-1182.

²² NARZIYEVA, I. Z. (2021, March). COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE CULTURAL AND NATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MODERN UNITS OF ORAL SPEECH (based on Uzbek and English language materials). In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 285-289).

²³ Kadirova, N. A. (2020). UZBEK NATIONAL CHILDRENS CLOTHING AND ITS EVOLUTION. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (6), 155-157.

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